

Appendix C

Depiction of the study procedure

Note. The flow chart depicts the single steps of the study procedure. The steps in the grey boxes are repeated for each of the three scenarios presented. The presentation order of the scenarios within the experimental conditions was individually randomized to avoid order and position effects. CR = crisis responsibility.